

Contributory Factors to Anaemia in Pregnancy in Benin City, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

About a third of the world population is affected by anaemia, with most of this burden on developing countries, Nigeria inclusive. Anaemia, though preventable, is a major contributor to maternal morbidity and mortality. Factors associated with anaemia in pregnancy include poor nutrition, socio-cultural behaviours and certain infections. We studied the habits, dietary diversity and pattern of infections that may explain occurrence of anaemia in 386 pregnant women (18-45years old) attending antenatal care at the Stella Obasanjo Women and Children Hospital (SOWCH) and the Central Hospital in Benin City, Nigeria between July-December, 2019. Data obtained was analyzed using SPSS version 26.0 and level of significance (p) set at ≤ 0.05 . The mean age (\pm SD) of the study population was 30 ± 4 years, 20 (5.2%) women had positive MP, 11 (2.8%) were HIV positive, 3 (0.8%) were HBsAg positive while none was found with a reactive anti-HCV. The mean Hb (\pm SD) was 10.9 ± 1.1 g/dl. The prevalence of anaemia was 45.6% with only mild and moderate forms recorded. Factors associated with anaemia were non-usage of insecticide treated net ($p = 0.03$), alcohol consumption during pregnancy ($p = 0.00$) and HIV infection ($p = 0.01$). There was a significant correlation between Hb and gestational age ($p = 0.00$) as well as duration of last child birth ($p = 0.02$). The mean Women Dietary Diversity Score (WDDS) (\pm SD) was 9 ± 1 , with 99.0% participants having a high WDDS. There was no association between WDDS and occurrence of anaemia. The high burden of anaemia persists. Health promotion strategies to limit factors associated with anaemia in pregnancy are advocated. We recommend further studies on the role dietary diversity plays on anaemia occurrence in our environment. .

Keyword: Anaemia, Dietary diversity, Alcohol in pregnancy, HIV infection, Malaria

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INTRODUCTION

Anaemia is the reduction in oxygen carrying capacity due to reduced haemoglobin concentration (Hb) expected for age, sex and specific environment.¹ About a third of the world population is affected, with most of this burden on developing countries, Nigeria inclusive.² Women, especially of child bearing age, and children under 5 years are prone to anaemia due to demands specific to their physiologic states as well as increased susceptibility to concurrent infections.² Worldwide, about 42% of pregnant women are anaemic.^{1,3} In developed countries such as America and France, the prevalence of anaemia in pregnancy was found to be 24.1% and 15.8% respectively.^{4, 5} Higher values have been reported in Asia and Africa. Values observed in Turkey and India were 74.1% and 64% respectively.^{6,7} In Ghana, one study showed 77.5% pregnant women were anaemic.⁸ The prevalence of anaemia reported among pregnant women in south-east Nigeria was 77%.⁹ In Okada, Edo state, 49.3% of studied pregnant women were found to be anaemic.¹⁰ According to the World Health Organization (WHO), any country with prevalence of anaemia at 40% or higher in vulnerable groups has a severe public health problem.¹¹ Maternal anaemia, though preventable, is a major contributor to maternal morbidity and mortality. Anaemia is estimated to contribute to more than 115,000 maternal deaths and 591,000 prenatal deaths globally per year.¹²

Factors associated with anaemia in pregnancy include multiparity, poor nutrition, low maternal educational status and other sociocultural factors.^{13,14} These include observance of food taboos and herbal medication use during pregnancy. Some of the herbal concoctions contain alcohol which contributes to the burden of anaemia in exposed mothers.¹⁵ Economic factors which affect health seeking behavior have also been implicated in anaemia occurrence, as well as in compliance with expected standard of medical care. Women of low socio-economic status find it difficult to

seek antenatal care, eat an adequate diet or adhere to prescribed supplements due to financial incapacitation.^{13,14,16}

Nutritional anaemia accounts for most cases of anaemia in pregnancy with iron deficiency being a leading cause.¹⁷ The lack of other food nutrients such as vitamin B12, A and folate may lead to anaemia.¹⁷ Pregnant women are at a higher risk because of increased nutritional demands necessary for foetal growth and development.¹⁸ An association between low dietary diversity and anaemia has been established.¹⁹ Pregnant women are also physiologically prone to dilutional anaemia from increased plasma volume expansion relative to red cell mass, however, this may become pathological.¹⁷ In Africa, common infections that predispose to anaemia include malaria, helminthiasis and Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infection.²⁰

²¹ Pregnant women are prone to these infections due to a relative immunosuppression in this physiologic state.²⁰

²¹ A form of aplastic anaemia has also been identified in pregnancy, whether related to viral hepatitis infection or not.

Anaemia during pregnancy has adverse effects on both mother and the unborn child. It is associated with increased maternal morbidity and mortality, impaired lactation, prematurity, low birth weight or intrauterine fetal death at the extreme.²² Anaemia also has devastating costs to individual and national productivity. Women with anaemia in pregnancy have decreased work capacity. They may be unable to earn their livelihood especially when their work involves manual labour.^{20, 23} It is therefore pertinent to identify factors associated with anaemia in pregnancy, and to mitigate them where possible. There is paucity of data on anaemia and its contributory factors among women in Benin City, Nigeria. The objective of this study was to determine the prevalence of anaemia and identify factors associated with it in pregnant women. This is with a view to bridging the existing knowledge gap and

assisting relevant authorities in policy making towards better maternal health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a cross-sectional observational study that involved consenting pregnant women (18-45 years old) attending antenatal clinic at the Stella Obasanjo Women and Children Hospital (SOWCH) and the Central Hospital, all located in Benin-City, Nigeria. Ethical clearance was granted by the Edo State Hospital Management Board, with reference number, CH/A40/56. Those who carried multiple gestation, had chronic co-morbidities or conditions predisposing to anaemia, such as haemolytic anaemias, or were actively bleeding or recently transfused with blood (<3 months) were excluded from the study. Using a systematic random sampling technique, participants were recruited for the study (based on the calculated sample size using the formula: $n = Z^2 P(1-P)/d^2$ within a period of 6 months (July-December, 2019). Each participant was administered a questionnaire which addressed demographic parameters, social habits, relevant obstetric history to the study, as well as a dietary recall table. Educational level was categorized as low (primary school or no formal education) or high (at least secondary school education and above). Income was divided into those who earned below or above the Nigerian minimum wage.²⁴ The Women Dietary Diversity Score (WDDS) by Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) was adopted to calculate the number of food groups consumed by the individual respondent over the previous 24-hour recall period.²⁵ Food consumed was grouped into ten, being roots and tubers, grains, pulses, nuts/seeds, meat/fish/poultry, milk/milk products, vitamin A-rich dark green leafy vegetables, other vitamin A-rich vegetables/ fruits, other vegetables, and other fruits. Obtainable score ranged from 0-10. Scores were divided into low (0-4) or high (5-10) dietary diversity.

About 5mls of venous blood was then drawn

aseptically into ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA) anticoagulated bottle to determine Hb concentration, analysed within 4 hours of collection using the Sysmex KX-219 (2006) haemato-analyser. Anaemia was determined using WHO criteria; first and third trimester: <11.0 g/dL; second trimester: <10.5 g/dL; mild (9.0-10.9g/dl), moderate (7-8.9g/dl), severe (4-6.9g/dl) and very severe anaemia (<4g/dl).¹ The remnant sample was then centrifuged to obtain plasma which was decanted into a freshly labeled sterile specimen bottle. This was used to determine malaria parasitaemia (MP), Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg), antibody to Hepatitis C (anti-HCV) and HIV reactivity using rapid test kits.

Data obtained was analysed using SPSS version 26.0 statistical package. Mean and standard deviation (SD) were used to describe continuous variables and proportions for categorical data. Chi-square analysis was used for group comparisons to determine the significance of observed differences or association where applicable. Pearson's correlate was used for correlation between continuous variables. Level of significance (p) was set at ≤ 0.05 .

RESULTS

A total of 386 pregnant women with a singleton gestation participated in this study. Table 1 shows their socio-demographic and clinical details. The mean age (\pm SD) of the study population was 30 ± 4 years, while mean gestational age was 31 ± 5 weeks. Majority of the women (318; 82.4%) were in their third trimester, 67 (17.4%) and one (0.2%) in second and first trimesters respectively. Most of the women (328; 99.0%) had a high educational exposure. Those who earned above the national minimum wage were 171 (44.3%). Eighty-one (21.0%) of the respondents were grand multiparous. A low duration of last child birth (<2 years) was found in 52 (13.5%) versus 334 (86.5%) with a high duration (≥ 2 years). Of the studied women, 134 (34.7%) had had an abortion, while 78 (20.2%) had had a miscarriage.

Table 2 depicts the habits of the participants. Only 80 (20.7%) used insecticide treated net (ITN). Seventy-eight (20.2%) women admitted to herbal medication use while 46(11.9%) consumed alcohol during current pregnancy. Food taboos were observed by only seven (1.8%) of the women while 72(18.7%) had a history of pica(ice> chalk/clay> paper>sand, as in Figure 1). The mean WDDS (\pm SD) was 9 ± 1 , with 99.0% (382/386) participants having a high WDDS. Table 3 shows the distribution of food groups consumed by the respondents. There was a statistically significant positive correlation between WDDS and income ($p=0.01$, $r=0.12$), but none with age ($p=0.12$ $r=0.07$) and educational status ($p=0.7$, $\chi^2=0.62$) as shown in Table 4. Twenty (5.2%) women had positive MP, 11 (2.8%) were HIV positive, three (0.8%) were HBsAg positive while none was found with a reactive anti-HCV. The mean Hb (\pm SD) was 10.9 ± 1.1 g/dl. The prevalence of anaemia was 45.6% (176/386). Majority of the women had a normal Hb (210; 54.4%), 163(42.2%) had mild anaemia and 13 (3.4%) had moderate anaemia. There was no one with severe anaemia. Factors associated with anaemia were lack of ITN use ($p=0.03$, $\chi^2=4.56$), alcohol consumption during pregnancy ($p=0.00$, $\chi^2=16.7$) and HIV infection ($p=0.01$ $\chi^2=5.98$) as in Table 5. There was a significant correlation between Hb levels and gestational age ($p=0.00$, $r=-0.18$) as well as duration of last child birth ($p=0.02$, $r=0.15$). There was no association between malaria parasitemia, previous miscarriage, pica, food taboos, herbal medication use, WDDS and occurrence of anaemia.

Table 1: Socio-demography and clinical parameters of the participants

Variable	Frequency (n=386)	Percentage (%)
Age		
<35years	319	82.6
\geq 35years	67	17.4
Educational status		
No formal education	4	1.0
Primary	31	8.0
Secondary	236	61.1
Tertiary	115	29.8
Employment status		
Unemployed	151	39.1
Employed	235	60.9
Income		
<₦18,000	215	55.7
\geq ₦18,000	171	44.3
Marital status		
Single	17	4.4
Married	369	95.6
Gestational age		
First trimester	1	0.2
Second trimester	67	17.4
Third trimester	318	82.4
Parity		
Nulliparous	0	0
Multiparous	305	79.0
Grand-multiparous	81	21.0
Duration of LCB		
Low (<2years)	52	13.5
High (\geq 2years)	334	86.5
Previous Abortion		
Yes	134	34.7
No	252	65.3
Previous Miscarriage		
Yes	78	20.2
No	308	79.8
Mean (\pm SD) age (years)	30 \pm 4	
Mean (\pm SD) Hb (g/dl)	10.9 \pm 1.1	
Mean (\pm SD) WDDS	9 \pm 1	
WDDS		
Low (0-4)	4	1.0
Adherent (5-10)	382	99.0
Occurrence of anaemia		
Anaemic	176	45.6
Non-anaemic	210	54.4
Distribution of anaemia		
Mild	163	42.2
Moderate	13	3.4
Severe	0	0.0

LCB- last child birth; WDDS- women dietary diversity score

Table 2: Some habits of the participants

Variable	Frequency(n=386)	Percentage
ITN use		
Yes	80	20.7
No	306	79.3
Herbal medication use		
Yes	78	20.8
No	308	79.2
Alcohol use		
Yes	46	11.9
No	340	88.1
Food Taboos observance		
Yes	7	1.8
No	379	98.2
Pica		
Yes	72	18.7
No	314	81.3

ITN- insecticide treated net

Table 3: Distribution of food groups consumed by participants

Variable	Frequency (n = 386)	Percentage
Grains	381	98.7
Roots and tubers	370	95.9
Pulses	359	93.0
Nuts/Seeds	362	96.8
Meat/Fish/Poultry	370	95.9
Milk/Milk products	341	88.3
Vitamin A-rich dark vegetables	365	94.6
Other Vitamin A-rich fruits/veg	330	85.5
Other vegetables	379	98.2
Other fruits	348	90.2

Table 4: Association between Hb, WDDS and selected variables of participants

Variable	Hb	
	r	p
Age	0.13	0.07
Gestational age	-0.18	0.00
LCB	0.15	0.02
WDDS	0.04	0.41
Variable	WDDS	
	r	p
Age	0.07	0.12
Income	0.12	0.01

LCB- last child birth; WDDS- women dietary diversity score

Figure 1: Pica distribution among participants (n= 72)

Table 5: Association between anaemia and some social, obstetric and clinical parameters

Variable	Anaemic, n (%)	Non-anaemic, n (%)	X ²	P value
Age			0.17	0.67
<35years	147 (46.1)	172(53.9)		
≥35years	29 (43.3)	38 (56.7)		
Multiparity			2.21	0.13
Nulliparous	0 (0)	0 (0)		
Multiparous	145 (47.5)	160 (52.5)		
Grand-multiparous	31 (38.3)	50 (61.7)		
Gestational age			4.23	0.12
First trimester	1 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
Second trimester	24 (35.8)	43 (64.2)		
Third trimester	151 (47.5)	167 (52.5)		
LCB duration			0.26	0.61
Low (<2years)	22 (42.3)	30 (57.7)		
High (≥2years)	154 (46.1)	180 (53.9)		
ITN use			4.56	0.03
Yes	148 (48.4)	158 (51.6)		
No	28 (35.0)	52 (65.0)		
Herbal medication use			0.02	0.88
Yes	141 (45.8)	167 (54.2)		
No	35 (44.9)	43 (55.1)		
Alcohol use			16.74	0.00
Yes	168 (49.4)	172 (50.6)		
No	8 (17.4)	38 (82.6)		
Food Taboo observance			1.91	0.15
Yes	171 (45.1)	208 (54.9)		
No	5 (71.4)	2 (28.6)		
Pica			2.20	0.13
Yes	38 (53.5)	34 (46.5)		
No	138 (43.8)	177 (56.2)		
WDDS			0.69	0.62
Low (0-4)	1 (25.0)	3 (75.0)		
High (5-10)	175 (45.8)	207 (54.2)		
MP			0.00	0.95
Negative	167 (45.6)	199 (54.4)		
Positive	9 (45.0)	11 (55.0)		
HBsAg			0.54	0.59
Negative	174 (45.4)	209 (54.6)		
Positive	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)		
HIV			5.98	0.02
Negative	167 (44.5)	208 (55.5)		
Positive	9 (81.8)	2 (18.2)		

LCB- last child birth; ITN- insecticide treated net; WDDS- women dietary diversity score; MP- malaria parasite; HBsAg- Hepatitis B surface antigen; HIV- Human immunodeficiency virus

DISCUSSION

Anaemia remains a cause of global concern in pregnant women. Finding amenable reasons for anaemia in these women is plausible, and that informed the decision for this research work. We studied the habits, dietary diversity and pattern of infections that may explain

Occurrence of anaemia in 386 pregnant women in Benin City, Nigeria.

Habits

Identified habits of the women studied included poor

usage of insecticide treated net (20.7%), a low frequency of herbal medication use (20.2%) and alcohol consumption (11.9%). Sleeping under an insecticide treated net helps to prevent against mosquito bite, an important factor in malaria transmission. Malaria is known to cause significant morbidity and mortality within children under five years as well as in pregnancy. It can also worsen pre-existing anaemia in pregnancy.²⁶ Though we found a low prevalence of malaria (5.2%) among these women, measures to reduce spread need to be emphasized. These include health education through various channels and at antenatal visits, providing insecticide treated net freely, as well as chemoprophylaxis to them has been well documented severally.^{27,28}

The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) describes any use of alcohol in pregnancy as significant and unsafe.²⁹ More women admitted to taking herbal medications than alcohol in our study. Though women may not take plain alcohol during pregnancy in Nigeria, they may consume herbal medications often. These locally prepared herbal concoctions usually contain alcohol and may predispose them to developing anaemia.³⁰ Significant alcohol consumption is associated with malabsorption and different red cell pathologies as well as foetal alcohol spectrum disorder.³¹ We found 11.9% of the women studied had consumed alcohol in their index pregnancy, unlike 59.2% reported in Bayelsa, Nigeria.³² The Bayelsa study also showed that many women don't know the adverse effects of alcohol on pregnancy.³² Awareness should be raised on alcohol effects and benefits of abstinence during pregnancy.

Dietary diversity

Nutrition is an important component in the outcome of a pregnancy. Dietary diversity is one of the ways to access nutritional status. A high dietary diversity guarantees the supply of macro- and micronutrients needed for both mother and her growing foetus.^{25,33} As nutritional anaemia accounts for a major proportion of

anaemia in pregnancy, an emphasis on good nutrition as well as supplementation is pertinent. The women we studied showed a high dietary diversity (99.0%), with only 4 of them falling short of consuming at least 5 food groups. These women consumed all food groups we assessed in reasonable proportion. Also, only a few of them observed food taboos, a fact which supports their understanding of the importance of good nutrition in pregnancy. Though most of our participants had a high dietary diversity than previously reported, we believe this may be due to difference in sample size, study area and level of education of the respondents in these studies.^{34, 35} We also found a positive correlation between WDDS and income. There have been conflicting reports on the association of dietary diversity and income.³⁶ However, earning an income influences purchasing power which includes food options. Food security is also guaranteed when an individual has a source of income.³⁷

Infections

We had a low prevalence of malaria (5.2%) compared to other reports in Nigeria.³⁸ Though we used a rapid diagnostic test, the gold standard for malaria diagnosis remains a blood film examination.³⁹ The prevalence of HBsAg among participants was also low (0.8%), as well as HIV (2.8%). We found no one with HCV infection. Ikeako et al found higher values in South-Eastern Nigeria, probably because they studied more women and used more sensitive assay methods.⁴⁰

Anaemia and associated factors

The mean Hb in this study was 10.9± 1.1g/dl. The work of Saaka et al in Ghana gave a close report to ours, while a higher value was obtained in Ethiopia by Grum et al.⁴¹ Our study showed that women with longer duration of last child birth had higher Hb (p= 0.02, r= 0.15). Grum et al equally found that birth interval was associated with anaemia when a bivariate analysis was conducted in their study.⁴² These findings corroborate WHO recommendation of at least 2years child spacing to

prevent complications such as anaemia in women.⁴³ As gestational age increases, the risk of anaemia increase due to increasing foetal growth and nutritional demands.⁴⁴ This may explain why in the studied women, there was a negative correlation between Hb and gestational age ($p=0.00$).

There was a high prevalence of anaemia (46.5%), just as demonstrated in other parts of Nigeria and Africa. Even higher values have been reported in earlier works.⁴⁵ The distribution of anaemia we found (mild more than moderate) was close to previous reports, save that we found no one with severe anaemia unlike others.⁴⁵

Factors significantly associated with anaemia included alcohol consumption ($p=0.00$), non-usage of insecticide treated net (0.03) and HIV infection ($p=0.01$). It is a well documented fact that HIV is associated with anaemia, even in pregnancy.⁴⁶ Infection with HIV may inhibit or destroy haemopoietic cells leading to features of bone marrow suppression, anaemia inclusive. The presence of anaemia in the face of HIV infection may also connote disease progression.⁴⁷ We however found no association between WDDS and anaemia. This is as reported in northern Ghana and Islamabad.^{36, 41} Our finding however contradicts that of other works.⁴⁸ Our study involved mostly educated women living in an urban setting, unlike the rural women in the study by Zerfu *et al.* Studies incorporating rural and urban participants within Nigeria are suggested for a broad view on this subject matter.

Limitations of the study

The findings of this study may not be a true representation of women in Benin City as it was an institution-based study and did not cover women living in rural areas. Dietary diversity was assessed by individual recall, and may be limited by memory of the participants. The prevalence of infections reported may also be underestimated as superior assay methods were not used due to resource constraint.

CONCLUSION

From this study, the high burden of anaemia persists. Factors associated with anaemia included non-usage of insecticide treated net, alcohol consumption and HIV infection. There was no association between dietary diversity and anaemia in our study.

Recommendations

Health promotion strategies to limit factors associated with anaemia in pregnancy are advocated. These include the provision of insecticide-treated mosquito nets and malaria prophylaxis, health education on transmissible infections in pregnancy and prevention methods, as well as dietary counseling sessions during pregnancy and lactation. Further studies to elucidate the role of dietary diversity on anaemia occurrence in rural and urban Nigeria are also highly recommended.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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REFERENCES

1. de Benoist B, McLean E, Egli I, Cogswell M. Worldwide Prevalence of Anaemia 1993-2005: WHO Global Database on Anaemia. WHO, Geneva, Switzerland. 2008.
2. World Health Organization (WHO). Anaemia. Available at www.who.int (Accessed 12/03/2019)
3. Sanghvi TG, Harvey PW, Wainwright E. Maternal iron-folic acid supplementation programs: evidence of impact and implementation. *Food Nutr. Bull.* 2010; 31: 100107.
4. Allen LH. Pregnancy and iron deficiency: unresolved issues. *Nutr Rev* 1997; 55: 91-101.

5. Harvey T, Zkik A, Auges M, Clavel T. Assessment of iron deficiency and anaemia in pregnant women: an observational French study. *Womens Health*. 2016; 12: 95102.
6. Davas I, Marangoz D, Varolan A, Akyol A, Baksu B. Gebelikte deęişik seviyelerdeki anemilerde demir alınımının maternal, doğum ve perinatal sonuçlara etkileri. *J Turk Soc Obstet Gynecol* 2008; 5: 174-81.
7. Suryanarayana R, Santhuram AN, Chandrappa M, Shivajirao P, Rangappa SR. Prevalence of anaemia among pregnant women in rural population of Kolar district. *Int J Med Sci Pub Health*. 2016; 5: 454-458.
8. Kordorwu HEM. Factors associated with anaemia in pregnancy among antenatal care attendants in keta municipality. A dissertation submitted to University of Ghana. 2018; 1-80.
9. Nduka FO, Egbu A, Okafor C, Nwaugo VO. Prevalence of malaria parasites and anaemia in pregnant and non-pregnant women in Aba and Okigwe towns of southeast Nigeria. *Animal Res Intl*. 2006; 3: 508 512.
10. Oladeinde BH, Omoregie R, Olley M, Anunibe JA. Prevalence of HIV and Anaemia among pregnant women. *North American J Med Sci*. 2011; 3: 548-551.
11. World Health Organization. Haemoglobin concentrations for the diagnosis of anaemia and assessment of severity. Geneva, Switzerland. *World Health Organization*. 2011. Available at <http://www.who.int/vmnis/indicators/haemoglobin.pdf>.
12. Edris M. Nutrition lecture notes for health extension trainees in Ethiopia, Gondar University, in collaboration with the Ethiopia Public Health Training Initiative (EPHTI), the carter center, the Ethiopia Ministry of Health and the Ethiopia Ministry of Education. 2004.
13. Stephen G, Mgongo M, Hashim TH, Katanga J, Stray-Pedersen B, Msuya E. Anaemia in Pregnancy: Prevalence, Risk Factors, and Adverse Perinatal Outcomes in Northern Tanzania. *Hindawi Anaemia*.2018; Article ID 1846280, 1-9. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/1846280>.
14. Amen A, Girmay K. Assessment of Anaemia and Its Associated Factors among Pregnant Women Attending Antenatal Care in Karamara Hospital Jigjiga Town, Eastern Ethiopia. *European Journal of Nutr Food Safety*. 2015; 5: 699-700.
15. Obi E, Akunyili DN, Ekpo B, Orisakwe OE: Heavy metal hazards of Nigerian herbal remedies. *Sci Total Environ*. 2006; 369: 35-41.
16. Anorlu RI, Oluwole AA, Abudu OO. Sociodemographic factors in anaemia in pregnancy at booking in Lagos, Nigeria. *J Obstet Gynaecol*. 2006; 26: 773736.
17. Harrison KA. Anaemia in pregnancy, In; Maternity care in developing countries. J. Carson, KA Harrison, S. Bergston (eds) RCOG press. 2001; 112 128.
18. Lindsay KL, Gibney ER, McAuliffe FM. Maternal nutrition among women from Sub-Saharan Africa, with a focus on Nigeria, and potential implications for pregnancy outcomes among immigrant populations in developed countries. *J Hum Nutr Diet*. 2012; 25: 534-546.
19. Hidru HD, Mengesha MB, Hailesilassie Y, Welay FT. Burden and Determinant of Inadequate Dietary Diversity among Pregnant Women in Ethiopia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Hindawi J Nutr Metab*. 2020, Article ID 1272393, 1-10. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/1272393>
20. Stoltzfus RJ, Luke M, Robert EB. Iron Deficiency Anaemia in Comparative qualification of health risk: Global and Regional Burden of Disease Attributed to Selected Major Risk Factors, edited by Majid Ezzati, Alan D. Lopez, Anthony Rodgers, and Christopher J. L. Murray, 163209. Geneva, Switzerland; World Health Organization.

- 2004.
21. Agu PU, Ogboi JS, Akpoigbe K, Okeke T, Ezugwu E. Impact of *Plasmodium falciparum* and hookworm infections on the frequency of anemia in pregnant women of rural communities in Enugu, South East Nigeria. *Pan Afr Med J*. 2013; 14: 27.
 22. Kumar P, Pore P, Patil U. Maternal anaemia and its impact on perinatal outcome in a tertiary care hospital of Pune, in Maharashtra. *Indian J Basic Appl Med Res*. 2012; 1: 111-119.
 23. McLean, E, Cogswell M, Egli I, Wojdyla D, de Benoist B. Worldwide prevalence of anaemia, WHO, vitamin and mineral nutrition information system. 1993-2005. *Public health nutr*. 2009; 12: 444-454.
 24. Nigerian National Minimum wage amended Act (2011). Available at www.ilo.org/docs
 25. FAO and FHI, Minimum Dietary Diversity for Women: A Guide for Measurement, FAO, Rome, Italy, 2016.
 26. Olukosi A, Afolabi BM. Malaria and anaemia among pregnant women living in communities along the coast of Lagos Lagoon, South-west Nigeria. *Int J Pregn & Chi Birth*. 2018;4: 175–182.
 27. World Health Organization. A Strategic Framework for Malaria Prevention and Control During Pregnancy in the African Region. AFR/MAL/04/01. Brazzaville: WHO Regional Office for Africa; 2004.
 28. Federal Ministry of Health. National Antimalarial Treatment Guideline. Abuja: FMOH; 2005
 29. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Foetal Alcohol Spectrum Disorders. Available at www.cdc.gov/vncbddd/fasd/alcohol-use.html
 30. Kehinde OS, Adegoke AE. Taking alcohol by deception: an analysis of ethanol concentration of “paraga” an alcoholic herbal mixture in Nigeria. *BMC Res Notes*. 2012; 5:127. Available at <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1756-0500/5/127>
 31. Onwuka CI, Ugwu EO, Dim CC, Menuba IE, Iloghalu EI, Onwuka CI. Prevalence and Predictors of Alcohol Consumption during Pregnancy in South-Eastern Nigeria. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2016; 10: 10-13.
 32. Ordinioha B, Brisibe S. Alcohol consumption among pregnant women attending the ante-natal clinic of a tertiary hospital in South-South Nigeria. *Niger J Clin Pract*. 2015; 18: 13-17.
 33. Sholeye OO, Badejo CA, Jeminusi OA. Dietary habits of pregnant women in Ogun-East Senatorial Zone, Ogun State, Nigeria: A comparative study. *Int J Nutr Metabolism*. 2014; 6: 42-49. DOI: 10.5897/IJNAM2014.0170
 34. Kever RT, Martins SD, Lola N, Dathini H, Habu H, Fatima AA, et al. Knowledge and attitude of pregnant Women towards dietary practices in Yerwa Clinic, Maiduguri Metropolitan Council; Borno State Nigeria. *J Res Nurs Midwifery*. 2015; 4: 1219. Available at <https://doi.org/10.14303/jrnm.2014.027>.
 35. Ehwarieme AT, Amiegheme EF, Enosekhafoh B. Knowledge and practice of healthy nutrition among pregnant women attending antenatal clinic at selected private hospitals in Benin City. *Int J Nursing and Midwifery*. 2019; 11: 75-86. DOI: 10.5897/IJNM2019.0379.
 36. Ali F, Thaver I, Khan SA. Assessment of dietary diversity and nutritional status of pregnant women in Islamabad, Pakistan. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad*. 2014; 26: 506509.
 37. McDonald CM, McLean J, Kroeun H, Talukder A, Lynd LD, Green TJ. Household food insecurity and dietary diversity as correlates of maternal and child undernutrition in rural Cambodia. *Euro J Clin Nutr*. 2015; 69: 242246.
 38. Oladeinde BH, Omoregie R, Odia I, Oladeinde OB. Prevalence of Malaria and Anaemia among Pregnant Women Attending a Traditional Birth Home in Benin City, Nigeria. *Oman Med J*. 2012; 27: 232-236. DOI 10. 5001/omj.2012.52

39. Mathison BA, Pritt BS. Update on malaria diagnostics and test utilization. *J Clin Microbiol.* 2017; 55: 2009-2017. <https://doi.org/10.1128/JCM.02562-16>.
40. Ikeako LC, Ezegwui HU, Ajah LO, Dim CC, Okeke TC. Seroprevalence of Human Immunodeficiency Virus, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, Syphilis, and Co-infections among Antenatal Women in a Tertiary Institution in South East, Nigeria. *Ann Med Health Sci Res.* 2014; 4: 954-958. DOI: 10.4103/2141-9248.144925.
41. Saaka M, Oladele J, Larbi A, Hoeschle-Zeledon I. Dietary Diversity Is Not Associated with Haematological Status of Pregnant Women Resident in Rural Areas of Northern Ghana. *Hindawi J Nutr Metab.* 2017; Article ID 8497892, 1-10. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/8497892>.
42. Grum T, Brhane E, Hintsu S, Kahsay G. Magnitude and factors associated with anemia among pregnant women attending antenatal care in public health centers in central zone of Tigray region, northern Ethiopia: a cross sectional study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2018; 18: 433. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-018-2063-z>.
43. Report of a WHO Technical Consultation on Birth Spacing. World Health Organization, 2006. Available at www.who.int.
44. Bothwell TH. Iron requirements in pregnancy and strategies to meet them. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2000; 72: 257S-264S.
45. Sholeye OJ, Animashaun VJ, Shorunmu TO. Anaemia in pregnancy and its associated factors among primary care clients in Sagamu, Southwest, Nigeria: A facility-based study. *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2017; 6: 323-329.
46. Okeudo C, Ezem BU, Ojiyi EC, Anolue FC, Dike EI. Prevalence of anaemia among *Human Immune-Deficiency virus (HIV)* positive pregnant women at booking in Orlu, in South-Eastern Nigeria. *Afr Med J.* 2014; 5(1): 45-49.
47. Tunkyia K, Moodley J. Anaemia in pregnancy in a setting of high *HIV* prevalence rates Kay. *South Afr Inf Dis.* 2017; 32: 138-141.
48. Zerfu TA, Umeta M, Baye K. Dietary diversity during pregnancy is associated with reduced risk of maternal anemia, preterm delivery, and low birth weight in a prospective cohort study in rural Ethiopia. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2016; 103: 1482-1488.